

TWINNED
By Stars

D5.3 REPORT ON D&C ACTIVITIES 1

WP5 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

TWINNEDBYSTARS

**UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND
DIGITALISATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED
ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES, AND BUSINESSES IN ORS**

GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101124900

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Version history

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	17/09/2024	Draft version sent to Steering Committee for comments	Silvia Pérez Palomo, Beatrice Avagnina, Sara Rebollo Ramírez
1.0	30/09/2024	Final version to be submitted after inclusion of comments from the Steering Committee	Silvia Pérez Palomo, Beatrice Avagnina, Sara Rebollo Ramírez
2.0	18/10/2024	Deliverable updated as per EC review	Silvia Pérez Palomo

Deliverable information

Project Acronym	TWINNEDbySTARS	
Project Title	Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs	
Type of action	EMFAF Project Grants	
Topic	EMFAF-2023-PIA-FLAGSHIP-5-OR	
Project Start Date	01/10/2023	
Project Duration	36 months	
Work Package	WP5 – COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION	
Deliverable	D5.3 REPORT ON D&C ACTIVITIES 1	
Due Date	30/09/2024	
Submission Date	18/10/2024	
Dissemination Level ¹	PU - Public	
Deliverable Responsible	CE (CONSULTA EUROPA)	
Version	2.0	
Status	Final	
Author(s)	Silvia Pérez, Beatrice Avagnina, Sara Rebollo Ramírez	CE
Reviewer(s)	Steering Committee members	

¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive

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Acronyms & abbreviations

D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
CE	Consulta Europa
EU	European Union
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
T.no	Task
R&I	Research and Innovation

1. Executive summary

TWINNEDbySTARS seeks to enhance the competitiveness of the maritime tourism sector in Outermost Regions while contributing to the protection of marine biodiversity, preserving cultural heritage, and developing marine astro tourism by highlighting ancient navigational routes as sustainable destinations for these remote areas. Additionally, the project aims to strengthen existing partnerships, build capacity, and co-create tourism products.

To achieve these goals, TWINNEDbySTARS plans to engage stakeholders at regional, national, and European levels through an inclusive process. The initiative will priorities the involvement of key sectors, including industry (especially businesses within the nautical value and supply chain in participating regions), civil society (such as sailors' and consumers' associations), public administrations (including tourist boards), and academia.

This report, part of Work Package 5, summaries the communication actions and activities carried out during the project's first year (M1/October 2023–M12/September 2024). It also serves as a reference for reviewing and refining the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) strategy for the next period (M12-M23). Updated versions of this report are anticipated at M24 and M36.

Finally, notable achievements include the project's presence at international events, recognition by the funding entity CINEA in their online publications, and even feature in their videos on YouTube.

This is a public document that will be available on the official project website, upon approval: www.twinnedbystars.eu.

2. Introduction

This document presents the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the first year (M1 - M12) in the framework of the TWINNEDbySTARS project. The project, which aims to turn the European Outermost Regions into an internationally recognised maritime ecotourism destination, has prioritised effective communication of its progress and results. Dissemination actions have been also essential to increase the visibility of the project, engage stakeholders and encourage the adoption of good practices related to marine biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation and astro-tourism.

Throughout this period, communication and dissemination strategies have been implemented targeting both specialised and general audiences, using a variety of channels and tools.

2.1 Project background

TWINNEDbySTARS aims to merge tourism, marine biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation, and astrotourism to turn the European ORs into a prestigious maritime ecotourism destination. TWINNEDbySTARS promotes ecotourism through on-board marine education, courteous navigation, and unique experiences that reinforce responsible behaviour, building on previous initiatives in the Macaronesian region. The project fosters digital and ecological innovation, strengthens partnerships, and opens doors for co-creation. With the support of experienced experts in the nautical tourism industry, it involves public and private entities in a phased process that starts with preliminary analysis, mapping, and training definition and continues with training implementation, marketing, and product testing.

Table 1. TWINNEDbySTARS consortium.

Partner No.	Participant organisation name	Acronym	Country
1	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	ULPGC/TIDES	ES
1.1	Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la ULPGC	FCPCT/ULPGC	ES
2	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation	CE	ES
3	Asociación Cluster Marítimo de Canarias	CMC	ES
4	Océano de Experiencias SL	NAUTIC OCEAN	ES
5	Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas	CETECIMA	ES
6	Associação MarinaFunchal	MARINA FUNCHAL	PT
7	Associação Comercial E Industrial Do Funchal	ACIF-CCIM	PT
8	Secretaria Regional do Mar e das Pescas	DRPM AZORES	PT
9	Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique	CTM	FR
10	European Boating Industry	EBI	BE

2.2 Objectives of the D&C report

This report serves as a project activity monitoring enabling the assessment of whether planned actions are being executed correctly and on schedule, as well as their effectiveness. This process allows for the refinement of the communication and dissemination plan to enhance its reach and impact.

This document is designed to disseminate and transfer the outcomes and results of all TWINNEDbySTARS activities to key stakeholders. The specific objectives are:

1. To enhance the project's visibility and raise awareness among the general public.
2. To facilitate stakeholder engagement.
3. To support knowledge transfer through both scientific and non-scientific publications, as well as the organisation of training events.
4. To establish connections with a broad network of EU projects (sister projects) and initiatives, enabling the exchange of experiences and the promotion of R&I activities.
5. To ensure effective internal communication among partners and monitor their activities.

Table 2. WP5 tasks' descriptions.

Task title		Task description
T5.1	Development of the D&C Plan	A Dissemination & Communication (D&C) Plan will be developed at M3 detailing target groups to be reached, communication channels, tools, and outputs to be used, and providing a calendar of D&C activities. The Plan will be periodically updated.
T5.2	Dissemination activities	A variety of materials and tools will be produced including the project website, logo and corporate image, layout, posters and roll-ups as well as banners for social media. It will also deal with the dissemination and promotion of the organised events, webinars, workshops and trainings from T5.3 as well as with other funded projects.
T5.3	Awareness raising activities and outreach to society	This task deals with the organisation of events, webinars, workshops, trainings or other dissemination actions.

During the first year of the project, WP5 has worked in close synergy with WP1 and WP2. The deliverable "D1.1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan," submitted in M11 (August 2024), has served as a key reference for planning and implementing D&C actions under WP5. In this sense, numerous emails targeting specific regional, national, and EU stakeholders have been sent to inform them about the project and invite them to join the TWINNEDbySTARS network. Additionally, several social media campaigns have been designed, and various consortium partners have actively participated in events at the European level to further attract companies to the project. Likewise, WP5 has played a significant role in advancing WP2, which aims to increase awareness, motivation, and skills and provide tools to tourism firms and decision-makers in the context of coastal and maritime tourism.

2.3 Target groups

Similarly, a stakeholder’s identification process has been carried out through different tasks within this reports time framework, mainly at WP1 and WP5. For this purpose, a mapping of actors (task 1.1) of the quadruple helix and a Stakeholder Engagement Plan has been previously conducted to ensure a wide representation of these stakeholders as target groups in the communication and dissemination actions within the project. The stakeholder’s engagement tasks will remain active during the whole life of the project.

TWINNEDbySTARS is targeting representatives of the Quadruple Helix Model recognising four major actors in the innovation system:

Table 3. Target groups description.

TARGET GROUP	DESCRIPTION
Science stakeholders	Includes a diverse network of actors managing, coordinating, or conducting scientific research related to greening activities and innovation. This group brings in the research community, science managers as well students and PhD scientists at local, national, intergovernmental, and EU levels as well as representatives of other EU projects.
Policy makers	Representatives of private or public institutions of local, national and global governance, promotion, environmental management and regulation of tourism and nautical activities. Directorates-General (RTD, CLIMA, ENER, ENV, MARE), the JRC, European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency; the European Parliament (intergroups, committees, MEPs), international Ocean governance initiatives, OECD Ocean Economy working group.
Industry	All companies related to nautical and marine tourism. It includes those offering sports and recreational activities at sea. It also includes enterprises selling nautical equipment, charter services, whale watching, nautical schools, and the ports and marinas offering berths and other services to yachts.
Society/public	Citizen science activities will be promoted as for the first group, environmental organisations, local action groups, and other type of associations will be reached to provide them with comprehensive information on TWINNEDbySTARS solutions and to foster social acceptance.

3. Methodology

At TWINNEDbySTARS, an extensive communication and dissemination strategy has been put in place to engage both the public and key target groups, including marine and maritime businesses, associations, academia and other interested parties.

To facilitate monitoring, partners are required to submit semesterly reports using a D&C template (see Figure 1 below). These reports cover activities such as events organised, social media outreach, news/press releases published, and presentations at conferences. Meanwhile, CE is responsible for monitoring website usage, social media engagement, and events organised under its purview. By analysing these reports, CE can provide recommendations to optimise future dissemination and communication efforts, ensuring a more targeted and effective approach.

Figure 1. Dissemination and Communication Template.

Press Releases							
Reporting period	Publisher	Publication date	Title	Location	Link	Outreach	Observations
RP1							

The main channels for TWINNEDbySTARS dissemination and communication actions are the following:

1) Website:

The website serves as a central platform for disseminating information related to the project. It includes project information, news & events, public project deliverables, newsletter, and multimedia resources. The website is regularly updated to reflect project developments and ensure clear communication with the project’s online wider audience. The TWINNEDbySTARS website was launched in January 2024, and it can be accessed by visiting <https://twinnedbystars.eu/>.

2) Newsletter:

The WP5 leader distributes a regular newsletter to keep subscribers informed about project progress, upcoming events, research results, collaboration opportunities and next steps in the project. This newsletter is emailed to website subscribers, including project partners, marine and maritime companies and stakeholders. The newsletter is also available on the website. The first TWINNEDbySTARS newsletter was distributed on 23 February 2024, and the next one on 26 September 2024. These newsletters are made available at <https://twinnedbystars.eu/newsletters/> after being sent to subscribers.

3) LinkedIn:

LinkedIn is being used to reach out to professionals and companies in the nautical and maritime sector. This platform allows sharing of project updates, activities, project meetings, ecotourism or

boating special dates or events, and networking opportunities. The profile is available at <https://www.linkedin.com/company/twinned-by-stars/posts/?feedView=all>

4) Facebook:

Facebook is used to reach a wider and more diverse audience. Project updates, videos, infographics and testimonials are posted. Facebook's interactive options, such as commenting and sharing, allows to better understand and connect with the audience. The account is available at: <https://www.facebook.com/twinnedbystars>.

5) Instagram:

Instagram is a more visual communication platform that allows sharing photos, short videos and stories that promote the project's activities, outreach campaigns, events and important moments. This platform is a perfect way to attract the attention of the public and encourage interest in the project's initiatives. It can be visited at <https://www.instagram.com/twinnedbystars/>.

6) X:

This channel is important for the project as it acts as a dynamic platform for real-time communication, engagement and information dissemination. Through X it is possible to reach a wider audience, share project updates, highlight key milestones and interact with stakeholders during various online campaigns and initiatives. The use of X within the project ensures that TWINNEDbySTARS' progress and achievements are accessible, timely and widely disseminated. Posts are available via <https://x.com/TwinnedbyStars>.

7) YouTube:

The TWINNEDbySTARS YouTube channel serves as a central hub for video content related to the project, with recorded webinars, expert interviews and demonstrations providing an in-depth view of the work being done. Thanks to its broad reach and engaging format, YouTube allows to connect with and inform the public effectively, as demonstrated by the inaugural video, the 'Star Tour' webinar, released in May 2024. Access to <https://www.youtube.com/@twinnedbystars> to visit the channel.

8) External Platforms:

By strategically combining the above communication channels, the reach and impact of different messages is maximised across different audience segments, fostering engagement and collaboration with marine and maritime businesses and various stakeholders. In addition, from M1 to M12, the EU Survey and Google Forms have been used to gather targeted feedback through tailored forms, for the stakeholder engagement activities, which were distributed to stakeholders and shared through social media platforms for increased visibility.

In addition, these links have been shared on social networks to increase their visibility and consequently increase participation.

Table below includes the links to access to the surveys and other forms created:

Table 4. Links to the Forms

Survey	Link	Type of survey
EU Survey	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/TWINNEDbySTARS.	This questionnaire was created to involve companies in the project.
	https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/twinned-for-smes.	This questionnaire was developed to gather information on the activity, needs and challenges of SMEs:
Google form	https://forms.gle/SsCp75bHF8d8D2uDA	This questionnaire collected all registrations for the stellar tour online event.
	https://forms.gle/4fu6gwjutMvUQAsQ7	This questionnaire is collecting users who will participate in the co-creation workshops in all regions.

4. Dissemination & communication activities

4.1 Visual identity

The TWINNEDbySTARS' logo is a visual representation that summarises the scope and values of the project. Its main design is a right-facing sailboat, representing the fundamental elements that define the project's mission: progress and innovation. The idea of constantly moving forward and exploring new opportunities is strengthened by the sailboat's forward motion.

The logo also has four stars representing the outermost areas of the project. Finally, a circle connects these components, which strengthens the notion of cohesion and unity between the different areas. The circle serves as a symbol of integration and connectivity, concepts essential to the goal of the TWINNEDbySTARS project.

Figure 2. TWINNEDbySTARS's logotype.

The logo uses the shades of navy blue and red, which are characteristic of the world of the sea. These colours not only reinforce the maritime theme of the project, but also evoke the qualities of stability, confidence (blue) and dynamism (red). These qualities are essential to represent an innovative and constantly developing project.

The main typeface of the TWINNEDbySTARS project is Montserrat, a typeface that adds modernity, legibility and professionalism to the visual design. Montserrat's geometric, sans-serif typeface is ideal for projects that seek to communicate innovation and progress because it increases the sense of clarity and precision. In addition, its clean, contemporary design makes it easy to read in a variety of formats, both digital and print, ensuring that the message is delivered effectively and coherently.

Figure 3. TWINNEDbySTARS' colours and typeface.

This logo was designed using a grid that helps to maintain consistent alignment and proportion in all of its elements. The grid ensures that the main components of the logo, such as the circular

icon containing the sail figure, stars and waves, along with the TWINNEDbySTARS text, are well balanced and proportioned. This grid system allows the design to be flexible and scalable, maintaining its visual consistency across different sizes and applications.

As for the minimum safe space, it refers to the area around the logo that must remain free of other visual elements to avoid distractions and ensure that the logo maintains its impact and legibility. The minimum safe space equals one square of the grid on each of the four sides of the logo. This minimum spacing ensures that the logo has sufficient breathing space and does not feel cluttered by other graphics or text.

In addition, a minimum size of 15 mm is set for the logo. This minimum size ensures that all details of the logo, including graphic and typographic elements, remain legible and recognisable, even when reduced to smaller applications of promotional materials.

Figure 4. Representation of the logo grid, the minimum safety space and the maximum reduction size.

The negative version of the logo is essential to ensure the versatility and coherence of the branding in different situations. The negative version of the logo, like the main logo, maintains the essence of the key elements (the sailboat, the stars and the circle), but adapts to different corporate backgrounds, allowing the logo to be legible and have a significant visual impact even in high contrast situations. The logo is presented in white with both a navy blue and red background so that all graphic elements are visible.

Figure 5. Negative version of the logo.

These guidelines have been established to ensure the correct implementation of the logo on all promotional materials. The proper use of the logo ensures that its clarity and visual strength is retained, regardless of the format or medium in which it is applied, from physical print to digital media.

4.2 Promotional materials

4.2.1 LEAFLET & FLYER

These key promotional materials have been carefully designed to inform the target groups about TWINNEDbySTARS' primary objectives, consortium members, and other relevant details, including how to join the project's networks.

Leaflets and flyers will be distributed by partners during relevant events and meetings, with each partner responsible for printing their copies. These materials will also be available in both digital and printable formats, ensuring broad dissemination through digital channels. The material can be downloaded at <https://twinnedbystars.eu/results/>.

Figure 6. TWINNEDbySTARS's leaflet.

What is **TWINNED**by**STARS** about?

TWINNEDby**STARS** aims to make the outermost regions more visible and well-known in the tourism industry. These regions play a crucial role in supporting EU environmental policies. The project will showcase the innovative potential of tourism in these regions, focusing on aspects like marine biodiversity, cultural heritage, and astrotourism. This will involve creating networks and frameworks for collaborative design and development of a unique marine ecotourism experience centred around navigation and stargazing.

Objectives:

- Strengthening and sustaining cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism within the ORs. This involves linking the quadruple helix and ensuring network homogeneity through the promotion of certifications and promoting a unified brand image.
- Upskilling and capacity building for tourism firms and stakeholders in coastal and maritime tourism (circular economy practices, digital transition, networking and innovation).
- Creating new spaces for the co-creation of innovative products and nautical tourism experiences (star tourism, marine ecotourism, sustainable Atlantic crossing using trade winds, and the application of virtual reality).

Grant agreement number: 101124900

Granting authority: European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency

Starting date: 1 October 2023

Project duration: 36 months

Funding rate: 85%

Grant amount: 996,630.11 €

www.twinnedbystars.eu

Methodology:

The viability of the project hinges on the execution of tangible activities involving both public and private entities that collectively represent the quadruple helix of the concerned regions. The envisaged collaboration is well-founded, drawing on the established working relationships among many of the participating entities from prior projects.

In the initial phase, activities such as analysis, mapping, stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and training definition will be implemented. Subsequently, the focus will shift towards training execution, implementation of the marketing and commercialisation plan, and testing of the developed product.

Figure 7. TWINNEDbySTARS's flyer.

4.2.2 ROLL UP

A standardised **roll-up** of 85 cm x 200cm has been deigned. It conveys key messages, branding, funding, the EU emblem, and promotional information about the project such as the consortium members, website, QR code and the social media channels. The roll-up is available to be printed and used by every partner to assist any on-site event. This roll-up design may also be used digitally to promote the project on different websites, platforms, digital newspapers and social media channels.

Figure 8. TWINNEDbySTARS's roll-up.

4.2.3 PPT's TEMPLATE

Consulta Europa, as the leader of WP5 – Dissemination and Communication, have elaborated the template of all promotional materials and reporting support documents as, for example, the Power Point Presentation's template or the Deliverable's template.

Figure 9. TWINNEDbySTARS PPT's template.

4.2.4 OTHER PROMOTIONALS MATERIALS

Specific events-oriented designs have been also elaborated, as for example the poster for the EU OCEAN DAYS.

Figure 10. EU Ocean Days' poster.

4.3 Website

The TWINNEDbySTARS website (<https://twinnedbystars.eu/>) has been released M3 (December 2023) and filled out with all relevant information about the project and the consortium. Each section is designed to provide stakeholders and the public with comprehensive information about the project's objectives, progress, and achievements:

Figure 11. TWINNEDbySTARS's website home page

Join the **TWINNEDbySTARS** network and make a contribution!

Join our crew can benefits you in variety of ways.

Be part of our community!

Upcoming events

17 - 19 / 09 / 2024
ICOE 2024: Uniting Global Ocean Energy Leaders in Melbourne

20 - 22 / 11 / 2024
EST-FRAN WEEK: Unveiling Cutting Edge Advancements in Marine Science and Technology

20 - 22 / 11 / 2024
Sun&Blue

News

CO-CREATION WORKSHOP
Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores, Martinique, Azores

Invitation to co-creation workshop for SMEs of the maritime tourism sector in the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores and Martinique

17 August 2024

The 'TWINNEDbySTARS' Project at the Olympic Port during the America's Cup 2024

16 September 2024

From 22 August to 16 October, the Port Olímpic is witnessing the presentation of the 'TWINNEDbySTARS' project, which is having a special...

Successful Completion of the Masterclass Sessions for SMEs in the Maritime Tourism Sector

16 July 2024

We have already finished our Masterclass sessions. Welcome to our Masterclass!

TWINNEDbySTARS Boosts Astrotourism with a Masterclass for SMEs in the Maritime Tourism Sector in the Canary Islands.

15 June 2024

Welcome to our Masterclass!

[READ ALL NEWS](#)

Posts from @TwinnedByStars

Twinned by Stars - EU Project

Únete a nuestra sesión de co-creación, donde daremos forma a ideas innovadoras para el futuro del proyecto TWINNEDbyStars.

21 y 24 de septiembre de 2024

Edificio Fundación Puerto Las Palmas

#Innovate #YTW #COPPA24

Twinned by Stars

Preparate para un evento único en Canarias

Únete a nuestra sesión de co-creación, donde daremos forma a ideas innovadoras para el futuro del proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS. Esta es tu oportunidad de colaborar, compartir y construir juntos!

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TWINNEDbySTARS

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4.3.1 WEBSITE IMPROVEMENTS

The initial structure of the website was created with the key sections: About, Partners, News & Events, and Contact. These sections provide a solid basis for communicating the project's mission, important partnerships, and latest news, as well as offering an accessible point of contact. Several new sections have been added to this basic structure with the aim of improving the user experience (UX), optimising navigation to make it easier to understand and more fluid. This makes it easier to access the information they are looking for and ensures a more pleasant and effective interaction with the site, increasing satisfaction and engagement.

- **General updates (based on the initial website structure):**
 - A newsletter section has been created to allow users who have not subscribed to the website to be informed of regular updates on the project, including news, events, and the latest developments. This tool is key to keeping the audience informed and engaged, facilitating ongoing communication, and providing a direct way to share the latest results and achievements.
- **Results section:** this section has been added in order to implement an effective dissemination strategy. The various public deliverables will be published here, as well as the promotional materials created for dissemination. This area allows both stakeholders and the general public to access the results in a clear way, ensuring transparency and fostering understanding of the impacts achieved.
- **Google Analytics:** A Google Analytics tag has been inserted on the website to measure and analyse visits and user behaviour. This tag has been implemented under the Global Site Tag (gtag.js), using the identifiers G-50BCGK4WCX. This allows the collection of valuable data that facilitates website optimisation, improving the user experience by analysing key metrics such as duration of visits, most viewed pages, and traffic sources.
- **Privacy and Compliance:** The Privacy and Compliance section has been created to ensure that the site complies with European and international data protection regulations. It is divided into two main parts:
- **Cookies Policy:** This section explains the use of cookies on the website, which are small text files stored on the user's device to improve their browsing experience. It describes the type of cookies used (technical, analytical, advertising, etc.), the purpose of each one, and how users can manage their cookie preferences. It ensures that users can accept or reject the use of cookies as they see fit, in compliance with the relevant regulations.
- **GDPR Compliance:** This part addresses compliance with the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which regulates the processing of users' personal data. The section details users' rights, including the right to access, rectify, or delete their personal data, as well as to limit or object to the processing of their personal data. It also explains the security measures adopted to protect users' personal information and how users can contact the team responsible for exercising their rights. In this way, secure and transparent browsing is guaranteed, ensuring that the website is fully aligned with current privacy and data protection regulations.

WEBSITE INSIGHTS

The following insights show the overall data in terms of statistics and interactions with the project's website since its launch at the earliest stage (M3) of the project:

Figure 12. Website insights.

TWINNEDbySTARS has achieved within the first year of the project a total of **1.800 visits** and approximately **5,300 page interactions**.

Analysis of the top 10 countries with the most visitors reveals that TWINNEDbySTARS has been predominantly visited by Spanish and Portuguese audiences since the launch of the website, followed by Germany and Belgium.

Figure 13. Ranking of the most visited countries on the unique users.

WEBSITE ARTICLES

Since M3 to M12 of the TWINNEDbySTARS project, a total of **32 articles** were published on the project’s website. These articles play a crucial role in informing and engaging the target audience, providing insights into the project's progress, key achievements, related industry news, and collaborative efforts. By systematically sharing detailed updates and reports, transparency can be ensured, and a deeper understanding of the work can be fostered among stakeholders, partners, and the wider community. It is vital to maintain interest and encourage participation.

Table 5. List of TWINNEDbySTARS’s website articles.

Date	Title	Link
13/10/2023	European Union Unveils Groundbreaking Initiatives for Sustainable Maritime Development	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/10/13/european-union-unveils-groundbreaking-initiatives-for-sustainable-maritime-development/
27/10/2023	Gran Canaria Hosts TWINNEDbySTARS Project, Pioneering Maritime Ecotourism Initiative	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/10/27/gran-canaria-hosts-twinnedbystars-project-pioneering-maritime-ecotourism-initiative/
02/11/2023	TWINNEDbySTARS Business Meeting – “EXPERIENCES AT SEA... PEOPLE THAT INSPIRE”	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/11/02/twinned-by-stars-business-meeting-experiences-at-sea-people-that-inspire/
14/12/2023	Canary Islands Shine as Host of the Ultraperipheral Regions Conference.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/12/14/canary-islands-shine-as-host-of-the-ultraperipheral-regions-conference/

26/12/2023	The Government of the Canary Islands presented the findings of the 2023 Report of the Observatory of Sustainable Tourism.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/12/26/the-government-of-the-canary-islands-presented-the-findings-of-the-2023-report-of-the-observatory-of-sustainable-tourism/
19/01/2024	Dive into Watersport Innovation with EBI at Boot Düsseldorf 2024!	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/01/19/dive-into-watersport-innovation-with-ebi-at-boot-duesseldorf-2024/
24/01/2024	Unlocking Innovation in the Blue Economy with the 'EU Blue Champions' Scheme	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/01/24/unlocking-innovation-in-the-blue-economy-with-the-eu-blue-champions-scheme/
31/01/2024	EU main achievements in 2023 in tourism	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/01/31/eu-main-achievements-in-2023-in-tourism/
01/02/2024	Venture Capital Investors Explore New Horizons in Sustainable Marine Transport	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/02/01/venture-capital-investors-explore-new-horizons-in-sustainable-marine-transport/
07/02/2024	Join the TWINNEDbySTARS Network	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/02/07/join-the-twinnedbystars-network/
20/02/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS at B-Travel 2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/02/20/twinned-by-stars-at-b-travel-2024/
23/02/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Joins Prestigious Lineup at European Ocean Days 2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/02/23/twinnedby-stars-joins-prestigious-lineup-at-european-ocean-days-2024/
15/03/2024	Discovering the ocean at European Oceans Days	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/03/15/discovering-the-ocean-at-european-oceans-days/
20/03/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Presented at the B-Travel Event in Barcelona by Nautic Oceans Partners	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/03/20/twinnedby-stars-presented-at-the-b-travel-event-in-barcelona-by-nautic-oceans-partners/
01/04/2024	The Art of Sailing is presented by Nautic Oceans!	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/04/01/the-art-of-sailing-is-presented-by-nautic-oceans/
18/04/2024	Nautic Oceans unveils commemorative event for World Night: TWINNEDbySTARS presentation	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/04/18/nautic-oceans-unveils-commemorative-event-for-world-night-twinnedbystars-presentation/
02/05/2024	University Institute of Tourism and Sustainable Economic Development Tides is looking for research talent for TWINNEDbySTARS project	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/02/university-institute-of-tourism-and-sustainable-economic-development-tides-is-looking-for-research-talent-for-twinnedbystars-project/
06/05/2024	Discover the Secrets of the Universe at the 'Stellar Tour' Event!	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/06/discover-the-secrets-of-the-universe-at-the-stellar-tour-event/

15/05/2024	The decade of success of the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund in ocean conservation.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/15/the-decade-of-success-of-the-european-maritime-fisheries-and-aquaculture-fund-in-ocean-conservation/
21/05/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Project joins European Maritime Day 2024 in Svendborg, Denmark	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/21/twinnedbystars-project-joins-european-maritime-day-2024-in-svendborg-denmark/
22/05/2024	The Stellar Tour's event ends with success.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/22/the-stellar-tours-event-ends-with-success/
24/05/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS to participate in FIMAR 2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/24/twinnedbystars-to-participate-in-fimar-2024/
31/05/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Participates in the European Maritime Day 2024 in Svendborg, Denmark	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/31/twinnedbystars-participates-in-the-european-maritime-day-2024-in-svendborg-denmark/
03/06/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS to Participate in 'Impulso Azul' on June 6th in Las Palmas	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/03/twinnedbystars-to-participate-in-impulso-azul-on-june-6th-in-las-palmas/
04/06/2024	The Partners of Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique Presented TWINNEDbySTARS at the Martinique Boat Show, 4th Edition	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/04/the-partners-of-collectivite-territoriale-de-martinique-presented-twinnedbystars-at-the-martinique-boat-show-4th-edition/
11/06/2024	TWINNEDbySTAR Shines at FIMAR 2024: A Boost for the Blue Economy	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/11/twinnedbystar-shines-at-fimar-2024-a-boost-for-the-blue-economy/
19/06/2024	CTM presents TWINNEDbySTARS to SMEs in the Martinique Marine Sector	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/19/ctm-presents-twinnedbystars-to-smes-in-the-martinique-marine-sector/
21/06/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS Boosts Astrotourism with a Masterclass for SMEs in the Maritime Tourism Sector in the Canary Islands.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/21/twinnedbystars-boosts-astrotourism-with-a-masterclass-for-smes-in-the-maritime-tourism-sector-in-the-canary-islands/
18/07/2024	Successful Completion of the Masterclass Sessions for SMEs in the Maritime Tourism Sector	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/07/18/successful-completion-of-the-masterclass-sessions-for-smes-in-the-maritime-tourism-sector/
21/08/2024	Invitation to co-creation sessions for SMEs of the maritime tourism sector in the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores and Martinique	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/08/21/invitation-to-co-creation-sessions-for-smes-of-the-maritime-tourism-sector-in-the-canary-islands-madeira-azores-and-martinique/
10/09/2024	The 'TWINNEDbySTARS' Project at the Olympic Port during the America's Cup 2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/09/10/the-twinnedbystars-project-at-the-olympic-port-during-the-americas-cup-2024/

24/09/2024	TWINNEDbySTARS brings together experts and SMEs from the maritime tourism and nautical sector in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/09/24/twinnedby-stars-brings-together-experts-and-smes-from-the-maritime-tourism-and-nautical-sector-in-las-palmas-de-gran-canaria/
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The table below lists the **25 articles that have been published on the project partners' websites so far**. Each entry includes the article title, publication date, and a link to the full text. These articles showcase the collaborative achievements, innovations, and progress made under the project.

Table 6. List of TWINNEDbySTARS articles published on project partners' websites.

Date	Partner	Title	Link
24/10/2023	FPCT-ULPGC	Europa impulsa el turismo marino sostenible en sus territorios ultraperiféricos con el proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/item/817-europa-impulsa-el-turismo-marino-sostenible-en-sus-territorios-ultraperifericos-con-el-proyecto-twinnedbystars.html
26/10/2023		El Parque Científico Tecnológico escenario de la presentación del proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS, una iniciativa pionera de ecoturismo marítimo	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/item/820-el-parque-cientifico-tecnologico-escenario-de-la-presentacion-del-proyecto-twinnedbystars-una-iniciativa-pionera-de-ecoturismo-maritimo.html
13/05/2024		Descubre los secretos del universo en el evento “Stelar Tour: Mythology, Starlight and Navigation Curiosities”, organizado por la ULPGC como parte del evento European Maritime Day in My Country, 16 de mayo de 2024	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/item/909-descubre-los-secretos-del-universo-en-el-evento-stelar-tour-mythology-starlight-and-navigation-curiosities-organizado-por-la-ulpgc-como-parte-del-evento-european-maritime-day-in-my-country-16-de-mayo-de-2024.html
24/09/2024		TWINNEDbySTARS reúne a expertos y PYME del turismo marítimo y la náutica en Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/en/noticias/item/985-twinnedbystars-reune-a-expertos-y-pyme-del-turismo-maritimo-y-la-nautica-en-las-palmas-de-gran-canaria.html
15/04/2024	TIDES-ULPGC	Los navegantes demandan marinas sostenibles	https://theconversation.com/los-navegantes-demandan-marinas-sostenibles-225826
23/10/2023		Twinnedbystars, un proyecto liderado en Canarias, para fomentar el	https://tides.ulpgc.es/twinnedbystars-un-proyecto-liderado-en-canarias-

		turismo náutico regenerativo	para-fomentar-el-turismo-nautico-regenerativo/
29/04/2024		La sostenibilidad en la navegación recreativa, examinada por tres investigadores de la ULPGC en The Conversation	https://www.ulpgc.es/noticia/2024/04/29/sostenibilidad-navegacion-recreativa-examinada-tres-investigadores-ulpgc
31/10/2023	CE	Launch of the TWINNEDbySTARS Project: Transforming Europe's Outermost Regions into International Maritime Ecotourism Destinations	https://consulta-europa.com/lanzamiento-del-proyecto-twinnedbystars-transformando-las-regiones-ultraperifericas-europeas-en-destinos-internacionales-de-ecoturismo-maritimo/
19/02/2024		Join the TWINNEDbySTARS Project	https://consulta-europa.com/unete-al-proyecto-twinnedbystars/
08/05/2024		TWINNEDbySTARS Invites to the 'Stellar Tour' Event: Discover the Secrets of the Universe!	https://consulta-europa.com/consulta-europa-invites-to-the-stellar-tour-event-discover-the-secrets-of-the-universe/
21/08/2024		We invite you to participate in the co-creation workshops of the TWINNEDbySTARS project.	https://consulta-europa.com/we-invite-you-to-participate-in-the-co-creation-workshops-of-the-twinnedbystars-project/
19/10/2023		Twinnedbystars, un proyecto liderado en Canarias, para fomentar el turismo náutico regenerativo	https://www.clustermc.es/twinnedbystars-un-proyecto-liderado-en-canarias-para-fomentar-el-turismo-nautico-regenerativo/
08/02/2024	CMC	Descubre el proyecto europeo TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.clustermc.es/descubre-el-proyecto-europeo-twinnedbystars/
03/06/2024		El CMC participa en el European Maritime Day de Svendborg, Dinamarca	https://www.clustermc.es/el-cmc-involucrado-en-el-european-maritime-day/
06/06/2024		Las Palmas de Gran Canaria y Viana do Castelo Impulsan la Economía Azul	https://www.clustermc.es/las-palmas-de-gran-canaria-y-viana-do-castelo-impulsan-la-economia-azul/
10/06/2024		CMC, FEDEPORT y el IFPMP Fomentan las Vocaciones Azules en FIMAR 2024	https://www.clustermc.es/cmc-fedeport-y-el-ifpmp-fomentan-las-vocaciones-azules-en-fimar-2024/

24/09/2024		El CMC fomenta la certificación del turismo náutico en el proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.clustermc.es/el-cmc-fomenta-la-certificacion-del-turismo-nautico-en-el-proyecto-twinnedbystars/
28/03/2024	Nautic Ocean	El turismo náutico en la Regiones Ultraperiféricas de la UE	https://www.nauticocean.com/blog/el-turismo-nautico-en-la-regiones-ultraperifericas-de-la-ue/
20/11/2023	CETECIMA	Kick off meeting article	https://www.cetecima.com/?p=4107
02/08/2024		CETECIMA aporta su 'know-how' para un turismo náutico sostenible en Canarias a través del proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.cetecima.com/cetecima-aporta-su-know-how-para-un-turismo-nautico-sostenible-en-canarias-a-traves-del-proyecto-twinnedbystars/
08/11/2023	MARINA FUNCHAL	Marina do Funchal presente no lançamento do projeto TWINNEDbyStars	https://www.marinadofunchal.pt/islandmadeira/marina-do-funchal-presente-no-lancamento-do-projeto-twinnedbystars/
30/10/2023	ACIF-CCIM	ACIF marca presença na primeira reunião de lançamento do projeto TWINNEDbySTARS	https://www.acif-ccim.pt/2023/10/30/acif-marca-presenca-na-primeira-reuniao-de-lancamento-projeto-twinnedbystars/?doing_wp_cron=1723371394.6771159172058105468750
16/11/2023	EBI	Presentation at EBI Council EBI Council Internal meeting INTERNAL	Microsoft PowerPoint - EBI Council - 16112023 - Full presentation (europeanboatingindustry.eu)
30/11/2024		EBI joins EU-funded TWINNEDbySTARS, Pioneering Maritime Ecotourism	https://www.europeanboatingindustry.eu/newsroom/newsletter/item/872-ebi-joins-eu-funded-twinnedbystars-pioneering-maritime-ecotourism
23/04/2024		Presentation at EBI Council EBI Council Internal meeting INTERNAL	Microsoft PowerPoint - EBI Council Meeting April Project Update 1 (europeanboatingindustry.eu)

It is worth noting that the project has been mentioned on the websites of the European Commission-CINEA.

Table 7. TWINNEDbySTARS articles published on CINEA website.

Date	Title	Link
Unknown	Project TWINNEDbySTARS	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/featured-projects/twinnedbystars_en

22/02/2024	Where next for Europe's Seas: the contribution of EU-funded projects at EU Ocean Days	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/eu-projects-sustainable-blue-economy-eu-ocean-days-2024-02-22_en
12/10/2023	New EMFAF Regional flagship projects just kicked off their work!	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/new-emfaf-regional-flagship-projects-just-kicked-their-work-2023-10-12_en

4.4 Newsletter

To effectively communicate the latest updates and achievements of the TWINNEDbySTARS project, WP5 utilises a dynamic newsletter as a key outreach tool. Newsletters are an invaluable resource for keeping stakeholders informed and engaged, offering a regular stream of updates on project milestones, new developments, and key achievements.

The inaugural edition was distributed on February 23, 2024, reaching a network of 108 recipients and published on the project's website to boost its outreach to new visitors. This newsletter not only highlights the D&C progress but also plays a pivotal role in fostering interest and involvement among stakeholders.

The final structure established for the first newsletter, launched in M5, included a series of sections designed to introduce and raise awareness of the project. It began with an introduction entitled Introducing TWINNEDbySTARS, followed by Meet TWINNEDbySTARS, where the project was introduced in more detail. The main objectives of the project were also addressed, along with a detailed explanation of who we are and what we do. In addition, readers were invited to become part of our community. A section dedicated to the latest news was included, as well as a part on related projects, also known as sister projects. Finally, readers were informed about upcoming events and next steps of the project.

Figure 14. First newsletter release

On 26 September 2024, the second newsletter, designed to provide recent project updates from M5 to M12, was published on the TWINNEDbySTARS website. In this edition, we have added the premiere of the project's first official video, as well as including recent updates and activities. This update keeps subscribers abreast of the latest developments and maintains commitment to the ongoing development of the project.

Figure 15. Second newsletter release.

The design of both newsletters has been developed in total coherence with the visual identity of the project, ensuring that all graphic elements faithfully reflect the image of TWINNEDbySTARS.

To date, **a community of 237 subscribers has received the project newsletter**, which closely follows the progress and evolution of the project. The newsletters are available at: <https://twinnedbystars.eu/newsletters/>.

Figure 16. Subscribers for the newsletter.

Moreover, partners have also featured the project in their own institutional newsletters:

Table 8. List of TWINNEDbySTARS articles published on project partners' newsletters.

Date	Partner	Title	Link
19/10/2024	CMC	“Experiences at sea: people that inspire”: business meeting with nautical and maritime entrepreneurs	https://mailchi.mp/clustermc/noticias-de-inters-17073632
14/02/2024		“Discover a word inspired by stars and the ocean”	https://mailchi.mp/clustermc/noticias-de-inters-17633444?e=b37857c7ff
13/05/2024		“Experiences at sea: people that inspire”:	https://mailchi.mp/clustermc/noticias-de-inters-17073632

		business meeting with nautical and maritime entrepreneurs	
31/12/2023	TIDES-ULPGC	Newsletter Diciembre 2023	https://tides.ulpgc.es/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Newsletter-Diciembre-23.pdf
31/12/2023	ACIF-ACCIM	Newsletter Dezembro 2023	https://mkt.acif-ccim.pt/vl/80053fa1e1260d2a7fa913ad58937331fdafd97fae1G9e1LLjfe1ozFe9-40-3510c
Unknown		Feiras Internacionais	Feiras internacionais (acif-ccim.pt)
Unknown		Conferência do Setor Náutico 2024	Conferência do Setor Náutico 2024 (acif-ccim.pt)
30/10/2023	EBI	EBI joins EU-funded TWINNEDbySTARS, Pioneering Maritime Ecotourism	EBI joins EU-funded TWINNEDbySTARS, Pioneering Maritime Ecotourism (europeanboatingindustry.eu)

4.5 Social Media

In accordance with the Grant Agreement, WP5 has established a presence on several social media platforms to reach a broader audience. The primary channels—X, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Facebook—allow connecting with a diverse range of target groups, including SMEs, policymakers, decision-makers, other stakeholders, and other EU projects and initiatives.

These accounts are regularly updated with valuable content such as project updates, news, digital campaigns, events, webinars, and other relevant activities. Their main purposes are:

- **Communication:** Facilitating real-time interaction and dialogue with the audience.
- **Information Sharing:** disseminating details about events, project activities, and sector news.
- **Community Engagement:** Building and nurturing a community around the project.
- **Promotion:** Highlighting project actions and achievements.
- **Networking:** connecting professionals and organisations, fostering collaboration, and creating opportunities for growth (including collaboration with sister projects).
- **Education and Awareness:** Raising awareness about the marine environment, blue and circular economies, and sustainable practices in ecotourism.

The following table shows a general view about the performance on each channel from October 2023 (M1) until September 2024 (M12):

Table 9. Social media channels.

Social media	Link	N° posts	Follower s
	TWINNEDbySTARS https://www.linkedin.com/company/twinned-by-stars/posts/?feedView=all	62	217
	@twinnedbystars https://www.instagram.com/twinnedbystars/	59	163
	Twinned by Stars https://www.facebook.com/twinnedbystars	59	47
	@TwinnedbyStars https://twitter.com/TwinnedbyStars	90	240

All social media campaigns are typically supported by a well-planned strategy, in line with the overall D&C plan of the project, that includes an event announcement post, engaging content or curiosities to build anticipation, and a reminder post as the event approaches.

In the second year of the project, work will be done to increase the numbers on social media. Strategies will be implemented to increase reach and engagement across all platforms, improving the visibility of the project.

4.5.1 SOCIAL MEDIA INSIGHT

- **LinkedIn**

The presence on LinkedIn has generated significant engagement, reflecting the growing interest in the TWINNEDbySTARS project. In the last 12 months, **20.316 impressions** have been reached, indicating the level of visibility the content has gained among industry professionals and stakeholders. These impressions highlight the effectiveness of the outreach efforts made and the relevance of the updates, which include project milestones, event announcements, and industry insights. In the future, LinkedIn will continue to be leveraged to expand outreach, foster connections, and raise awareness of key initiatives undertaken.

Figure 17. Content performance.

Metrics

• Facebook

Facebook activity has successfully captured the attention of a diverse audience, reflecting the widespread interest in the TWINNEDbySTARS project. Over the current analysed period, TWINNEDbySTARS posts have generated **24.646 reaches**, showcasing the content’s reach and engagement across the platform.

Figure 18. Facebook Growth.

- Instagram

The Instagram presence has been instrumental in visually engaging with the project’s audience and promoting the TWINNEDbySTARS project. The project has achieved **1.938 reaches**, highlighting the impact of its visually driven content on this platform. These impressions reflect the growing interest in the project’s updates, event highlights, and visual storytelling.

Figure 19. Instagram Growth.

- Twitter/X

Twitter activity has proven to be the most successful among the social media efforts, significantly amplifying the TWINNEDbySTARS project’s reach and engagement. During this reporting period, tweets have garnered 4.100 impressions, and 240 followers, showcasing the platform’s effectiveness in disseminating the content. These impressive metrics highlight the strength of the strategy in sharing timely updates, project news, and industry insights. Twitter will continue to play a crucial role in increasing visibility, driving conversations, and connecting with key stakeholders and the broader community.

Figure 20. Twitter Interactions.

4.6 Press releases

Press releases issued during the first year of the TWINNEDbySTARS project have been essential to disseminate the project’s achievements and broader developments. These official releases have been strategically created to keep the media and the stakeholders informed of the project’s progress.

This section includes a list of the **11 actions of earn media** that have been distributed, of which **1 is international, 2 are national (1 online press, 1 radio) and 8 are regional (5 online press & 3 radio)**, each highlighting the importance of their contribution to the promotion and dissemination of the project.

Table 10. Press release list.

Date	Title	Media	Type of media	Dissemination level	Link
Project launch & kick off meeting					
12/10/2023	New EMFAF Regional flagship projects just kicked off their work!	CINEA	Online press	INTERNATIONAL	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/new-emfaf-regional-flagship-projects-just-kicked-their-work-2023-10-12_en

18/10/2023	Twinnedbystars, un proyecto liderado en Canarias, para fomentar el turismo náutico regenerativo	El Espejo Canario	Radio	REGIONAL	https://www.elespejocanario.es/secciones/twinnedbystars-un-proyecto-liderado-en-canarias-para-fomentar-el-turismo-nautico-regenerativo/
27/10/2023	Gran Canaria organiza o proyecto "TWINNEDbySTARS"	Dnoticias	Online press	REGIONAL	Gran Canaria organiza o proyecto 'TWINNEDbySTARS' — DNOTICIAS.PT
01/10/2023	Madeira integra projeto europeu para a biodiversidade marinha e combate às alterações climáticas	O jornal económico	Online press	NATIONAL	https://jornaleconomico.sapo.pt/noticias/madeira-integra-projeto-europeu-para-a-biodiversidade-marinha-e-combate-as-alteracoes-climaticas/
12/07/2024	CETECIMA aporta su 'know-how' para un turismo náutico sostenible en Canarias a través del proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS	Puertocanarias	Online press	REGIONAL	https://puertocanarias.com/es/node/7520
Stakeholder engagement campaign and other project dissemination actions					
30/11/2023	Analizamos el estado de la acuicultura	RTVE audio Españoles en la mar	Radio	NATIONAL	https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/espanoles-en-la-mar/analizamos-estado-acuicultura/7025191/
05/06/2024	Canarias participa en el Día Marítimo Europeo	El Espejo Canario	Radio	REGIONAL	Canarias participa en el Día Marítimo Europeo (elespejocanario.es)
06/06/2024	El encuentro 'Impulso Azul' anticipa FIMAR 2024	RTVC Radio TV Canaria	Radio	REGIONAL	https://rtvc.es/el-encuentro-impulso-azul-anticipa-fimar-2024/
	El impulso de la economía azul en el entorno				

06/06/2024	atlántico, un esfuerzo conjunto entre Las Palmas de Gran Canaria y Viana do Castelo	Infopuertos	Online press	REGIONAL	https://infopuertos.com/lpgc-viana-do-castelo-impulso-economia-azul/
06/06/2024	El encuentro 'Impulso Azul' anticipa FIMAR 2024	Televisión Canaria Informativo	TV	REGIONAL	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5OFsi7HfpSA
27/01/2024	Projeto TwinnedbySTARs lançado em Canárias	JM	Online press	REGIONAL	https://www.jm-madeira.pt/economia/ver/221729/Projeto_TWINNEDbySTARS_la_ncado_em_Canarias

4.7 Events

Members of the consortium have participated offline and online at different events to promote the project and extend the network. These are the actions and events that have taken place during the first 12 months of the project:

Table 11. Attended events by TWINNEDbySTARS Consortium.

Partner	Type of event	Target group	Name	Location	Date	Link
TIDES-ULPGC, CETECIMA	Conference	Policy Makers	Impulso azul	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Spain)	06/06/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/03/twinnedbystars-to-participate-in-impulso-azul-on-june-6th-in-las-palmas/
TIDES-ULPGC	Conference	Industry	SSTD 2024	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Spain)	12-14/06/2024	https://tides.ulpgc.es/en/congreso-sstd/
CE, TIDES-ULPGC, Nautic Ocean	Conference	EU Citizens	EMD in my country - Star Tour	Online	16/05/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/22/the-stellar-tours-event-ends-with-success/
Nautic Ocean	Tourism Fair	EU Citizens and Industry	B-Travel	Barcelona (Spain)	16/03/2024	https://clusternautic.cat/2024/03/05/el-cluster-nautic-catala-i-12-empreses-associades-promouran-el-turisme-nautic-al-b-travel/
Nautic Ocean	Conference	Industry	The Art of Sailing	Barcelona (Spain)	01/04/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/04/01/the-art-of-sailing-is-presented-by-nautic-oceans/

Nautic Ocean	Conference	Industry	World Night	Barcelona (Spain)	15/04/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/04/18/nautic-oceans-unveils-commemorative-event-for-world-night-twinnedbystars-presentation/
Nautic Ocean	Conference	International Citizens and Industry	America's Cup 2024	Barcelona (Spain)	22/08/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/09/10/the-twinnedbystars-project-at-the-olympic-port-during-the-americas-cup-2024/
CE, CMC, CETECIMA, ULPGC	Fair	Industry	FIMAR 2024 (International Sea Fair)	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	8-10/06/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/11/twinnedbystar-shines-at-fimar-2024-a-boost-for-the-blue-economy/
TWINNEDby STARS consortium	EU event	Industry	European Oceans Days - Poster presentation	Brussels, Belgium	03/06/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/03/15/discovering-the-ocean-at-european-oceans-days/
EBI	Conference	Policy makers	Where next for Europe's Seas at the European Ocean Days	Brussels, Belgium	06/03/2024	https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/events/where-next-europes-seas-european-ocean-days-2024-03-06_en
EBI	Workshop	Scientific Community	Ocean Literacy in Action at the European Ocean Days	Brussels, Belgium	08/03/2024	https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/eu4ocean-coalition/ocean-literacy-action-european-ocean-days-2024-03-08_en
EBI, CMC	Conference	Industry	European Maritime Day	Svendborg, Denmark	30-31/05/2024	https://maritime-day.ec.europa.eu/index_en
CTM	Information meeting	Policy makers	Stakeholder's meeting	Digital platform	10/06/2024	N/A
CTM	Information meeting	Industry	Stakeholder's meeting	Martinique	14/06/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/06/19/ctm-presents-twinnedbystars-to-smes-in-the-martinique-marine-sector/
CMC	Conference	Industry	XIX Symposium on Marinas	Getxo, Bizkaia, Spain	25-26/04/2024	www.simposiopusertosdeportivos.es
CTM	Conference	Policy makers	The cultural, touristic and	Hôtel de l'Assemblée Collectivité	27/03/2024	N/A

			scientific sites in Martinique	Territoriale de Martinique		
CTM	Fair	French Maritime Industry	Martinique Boat Show	Port de Plaisance, Fort de France	30/05/2024-02/06/2024	https://www.martinique-boat-show.fr/
CETECIMA	Workshop	Policy makers	Presentation of Red CCF project (with a presentation of TWINNEDbySTARS project)	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	08/02/2024	N/A
TWINNEDbySTARS consortium	Conference	Industry	TWINNEDbySTARS Business Meeting – “EXPERIENCES AT SEA... PEOPLE THAT INSPIRE”	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	26/10/2023	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2023/11/02/twinned-by-stars-business-meeting-experiences-at-sea-people-that-inspire/

At the same time, during the first year of the project, two major events were organised by the project.

On the one hand, the ‘Stellar Tour’ was a virtual journey designed for young Europeans that allowed them to explore constellations and astronomical mythologies from the regions of the Canaries, Azores, Madeira, and Martinique.

On the other hand, a series of five masterclasses was held exclusively for members of our community. These masterclasses benefitted 55 small and medium-sized companies in the maritime tourism sector, offering training in local languages (2 in Spanish, 2 in Portuguese, and 1 in French) in astro tourism and digital strategies to attract customers, with the aim of providing key tools for the development and innovation of companies in the sector.

Work is currently underway to organise co-creation sessions in each region, which will take place this autumn.

Table 11. Events organised by TWINNEDbySTARS

Partner organisations	Type of event	Target group	Name	Location	Date	Link
TIDES-ULPGC, Nautic Ocean, CE	Conference Online	Citizens	Stellar Tour (EMD in my Country)	Online	16/05/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/05/22/the-stellar-tours-event-ends-with-success/
TIDES-ULPGC, Nautic Ocean, CE	Training	Industry	Masterclass on astro tourism and sailing for SMEs in the Canary Islands	Online	20/06/2024	https://twinnedbystars.eu/2024/07/18/successful-completion-of-the-masterclass-sessions-

			Masterclass on Experimentation and Online Tactics to Attract More Customers for Azorean and Madeira SMEs		26/06/2024	for-smes-in-the-maritime-tourism-sector/
			Masterclass on Experimentation and Online Tactics to Attract More Customers for SMEs in the Canaries		28/06/2024	
			Masterclass on astro tourism and sailing for for Azorean and Madeira SMEs		01/07/2024	
			Masterclass on Experimentation and Online Tactics to Attract More Customers for Martinique's SMEs		17/07/2024	

4.8 Advertising campaigns

4.8.1 STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT CAMPAIGN

As part of the stakeholder engagement activities promoted through WP1, a digital campaign targeting nautical and maritime SMEs was launched in four specific regions under WP5. The objective of the campaign was to capture the interest of businesses, policymakers, associations, and decision-makers and invite them to join this innovative network.

Moreover, the aim was to engage these businesses and motivate them to participate in strategic surveys to collect relevant information to share other relevant project activities, such as WP3 co-creation workshops and WP2 trainings. To this end, the WP5 campaign designed and used social media posts, posters and online banners.

Two surveys were designed and promoted among enterprises in each of the 4 regions, which are intended to gather essential information for capacity building and the creation of collaborative tourism products:

- Survey #1 – Introductory questionnaire to engage companies: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/TWINNEDbySTARSQuestionnaire>
- Survey #2 – Detailed questionnaire to gather information on companies' activity, needs, and challenges: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/twinned-for-smes>

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The surveys and many of the posters, publications, and banners were translated into the local languages of the participating regions to ensure greater inclusiveness and effectiveness of communication. In addition, all materials were designed to be inclusive, gender-balanced, reflect social diversity, and represent people with disabilities appropriately.

Figure 21. Poster for stakeholder engagement campaign.

Figure 22. social media campaign for stakeholder engagement.

Figure 23. Banner for stakeholder engagement campaign.

In the campaign that was designed to reach out to companies and encourage them to fill out the project surveys, Meta Ads were implemented, generating a total of 55,933 impressions and 15,420 views. Through these ads, 276 people clicked on the link to participate in the survey. During the campaign period, approximately 20 enterprises signed up for the survey thanks to the Facebook Ads.

Figure 24. social media campaign for stakeholder engagement.

4.8.2 SME CAMPAIGN MASTERCLASS

To reward the companies for their participation in the TWINNEDbySTARS project and to maximise the value of their involvement, **a series of free masterclasses were organised by the consortium and offered to the involved companies.** These sessions were specifically designed to provide them with valuable and practical knowledge that would enrich the value of their business.

The TWINNEDbySTARS masterclasses focused on key topics to boost the growth of SMEs in the maritime tourism sector. In the first one, entitled 'Experimentation and Online Tactics to Attract More Customers', participants learnt digital marketing strategies and innovative techniques to attract customers online, focussing on stargazing activities and obtaining Starlight certification, which allowed them to diversify their nautical offer. The second one, 'Astrotourism and its Potential for Your Business', highlighted the opportunities offered by astrotourism to deseasonalise demand, expand nautical services, and obtain Starlight certification, generating

greater value for businesses. Both sessions pointed to charter, sailing, catamaran, whale watching, and scuba diving companies.

The campaign to promote these masterclasses, conducted under WP5, included a variety of strategies. Content was posted on social media, which included short clips of the recorded sessions, encouraging companies to become part of the enterprise network of TWINNEDbySTARS. <https://www.instagram.com/p/C8rVhwjCm1x/>

In addition, an email campaign was launched for companies in the sector, inviting them to participate in the masterclasses. These emails provided details on the agenda and topics to be addressed and highlighted how companies could use the knowledge gained to boost their business. These emails were sent in local languages to ensure communication. Following the masterclasses, full recordings were sent to the companies so that they could review the content at their own pace

Figure 25. Email invitation to the Masterclasses

To access these sessions, companies first had to complete Stakeholder Engagement campaign survey designed to collect strategic data that would support capacity building and tourism product creation.

With this campaign, TWINNEDbySTARS not only rewarded the companies for their participation, but also provided them with valuable tools to further their growth and diversification in the maritime tourism sector.

4.8.3 STELLAR TOUR SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

In the framework of European Maritime Days in My Country, the 'Stellar Tour', a virtual experience for young Europeans interested in the cosmos and astronomy, was promoted. The event, which took place on 16 May 2024, included an online journey through the Canary Islands, Azores, Madeira and Martinique while exploring constellations, mythologies and astronomical curiosities. Participants discovered the history and meaning of the constellations over the course of 40 minutes, as well as the astronomical interpretations of ancient European cultures.

Figure 26. Stellar Tour online event

A social media campaign strategy including Instagram posts and stories was implemented to promote this event to reach out civil society and younger audiences. The content was aimed at attracting the attention of young Europeans, highlighting interesting aspects of the event and providing some basic knowledge. The target audience for this strategy had interests in astronomy and maritime ecotourism, as well as enthusiasm and participation.

The event was attended online by 49 participants.

Figure 27. Post of Social Media Campaign for Stellar Tour.

In the Instagram Stories, a star quiz was created and designed to capture the interest and participation of the young audience. The Instagram stories included two key questions related to the event themes. The following day, a video explanation was posted.

Table 12. Star Quiz.

Quiz	Question	Answer
Quiz 1	What is the relationship between mythology and the constellations Ursa Major and Ursa Minor?	<p>A) They are constellations that represent gods and goddesses in Greek mythology.</p> <p>B) They are constellations that play an important role in the legends and myths of different cultures.</p>

C) They are constellations that serve as a guide for travellers on the high seas.

D) They are constellations that symbolise the creation of the universe in Norse mythology.

Quiz 2 Which star in Orion's Belt helps us to know east and west?

- A) Rigel
- B) Betelgeuse
- C) Bellatrix
- D) Mintaka**

These Instagram stories not only informed participants about what they could learn at the event, but also actively engaged them in the astronomical theme of the Stellar Tour, building anticipation and excitement leading up to the event.

Figure 28. Stories of Social Media Campaign for Stellar Tour.

4.9 Video

4.9.1 OFFICIAL ANIMATED VIDEO

An official animated presentation video illustrating the objectives, challenges, partners and work packages of the TWINNEDbySTARS project is being produced. The animation is being produced by Help Studio, while the voice-over was done by Bunny Studio App. The video will be available in English and will be subtitled in the local languages of each region, including Spanish (ES), Portuguese (PT) and French (FR). The video will be available this autumn on the official TWINNEDbySTARS youtube channel: www.youtube.com/@twinnedbystars

Dissemination Strategy:

After its launch, the video will be promoted through a series of strategic actions to maximise its visibility. Firstly, it will be disseminated through a social media reel to capture the attention of the audience and generate interactions with the YouTube channel. It will also be highlighted on the TWINNEDbySTARS website to ensure its accessibility to all visitors. Project partners will be encouraged to share the video on their official networks, thus extending its reach across their platforms. In addition, the video will be integrated into the various future events related to the project to reinforce its presence and promote its impact on each occasion, and finally, it will also be available in the next newsletter planned for March 2025.

4.9.2 PARTNERS' TESTIMONIAL VIDEO ON SOCIAL NETWORKS

In order to raise awareness of our partners and their contributions to the project, a series of weekly publications are being carried out on social networks. Each week, a video testimonial recorded by one of the project partners is published. In these videos, each partner details their specific role in TWINNEDbySTARS, sharing their experience, contributions and the impact of their involvement in the project ensuring its outreach to the project's main Target Groups. This initiative aims to provide a closer and more personal view of those involved, highlight the diversity of efforts and strengthen recognition and collaboration within the partner network.

4.10 Synergies with other projects

On the TWINNEDbySTARS website and in the first two TWINNEDbySTARS newsletters, a specific section has been dedicated to related projects:

ECOROUTE

Ecoroute, dedicated to sustainable development in the Outermost Regions of the European Union. Aiming to transform these regions into smart destinations for nature and underwater cultural tourism, Ecoroute emphasises sustainable strategies, policy initiatives and community capacity building. More information about the project at: <https://ecoroute.eu/>

Callmeblue

Maritime clusters play a vital role in connecting public and private entities within the blue economy, fostering networking, technology transfer and innovation. The CALLMEBLUE project aims to strengthen cluster alliances in the Mediterranean, fostering North-South and South-South cooperation. By raising awareness and implementing concrete actions, including training programmes, the project strives to improve the sustainability of blue economy policies. Ultimately, CALLMEBLUE aims to strengthen the role of maritime clusters in fostering regional cooperation and supporting initiatives such as the UfM Ministerial Declaration and the WestMED Initiative. Find out more about the project at: <https://callme-blue.eu/>.

Sea Starlight

Sea Starlight is a national platform (in Spain) dedicated to offering exclusive nautical and astronomical experiences, combining activities along the Spanish coast, linking the sea with the starry sky. This initiative allows participants to enjoy sailing while discovering the mysteries of the universe through carefully guided astronomical observations. Learn more about the project at: <https://www.seastarlight.com/>.

MSP-OR

MSP-OR, is a project focused on maritime spatial planning (MSP). It supports competent authorities in the implementation of the EU MSP Directive (2014/89/EU), promoting its implementation in the outermost regions of the Azores, Madeira, the Canary Islands and French Guiana. Through this approach, MSP-OR contributes to more effective ocean governance, applying the Ecosystem Based Approach to ensure sustainable and well-planned maritime development. More information about the project at: <https://msp-or.eu/>

Fisatur

FISATUR is a project designed to boost the economic growth of coastal fishing regions. This project is closely linked to the local fisheries and tourism sectors, seeking the effective integration and promotion of Atlantic tourism products and services related to fisheries, aquaculture and maritime heritage. The objective of FISATUR is to evaluate and promote an innovative model of fishery-maritime tourism. This approach has the potential to transform the way we think about and use coastal resources, opening up new opportunities for sustainable economic development in these regions. Find out more about this project at: <https://www.fisatur.org/>

So far, during the first year of the project, contacts have been established with these initiatives in order to get to know each other's activities, objectives, and intended impacts. The projects have been disseminated by TWINNEDbySTARS through its online channels, and likewise, several of the sister projects have done the same for TWINNEDbySTARS.

In particular, it is worth noting that TWINNEDbySTARS invited the ECOROUTE project to give a presentation at its kick-off meeting. Similarly, TWINNEDbySTARS attended ECOROUTE's initial consortium meeting.

Figure 29. TWINNEDbySTARS coordinator presenting the project at the Ecoroute meeting.

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The plan for the next project phase under WP5 is to keep the contacts with the projects ongoing and assess additional potential collaborations in terms of joint events, policy recommendations, and results' sharing initiatives.

5. Results and evaluation of dissemination activities

Monitoring of the activities allows to assess if the actions planned are carried out properly and on time and to measure their effectiveness. Based on monitoring results, the project D&C Plan might be thus reformulated to improve the communication and dissemination outreach.

To monitor the project, partners are periodically requested to provide information on the activities carried out (for instance organisation of events, publications of news/press releases, etc., presentations at conferences) while CE is in charge of monitoring and reporting on the use of the website, social media, and on the events whose organisation is under CE's responsibility. Based on the reports submitted from the partners, CE can formulate recommendations for the future dissemination and communication activities.

See below the achieved results of the dissemination and communication actions carried out during the first year of the project:

Table 13. Monitoring and evaluation indicators' progress at M12.

Indicator	Results (M1-M12)
Participation of national/EU events	19
Production of newsletters	2
Newsletter subscribers	237
Nº of press releases	11
Website visits	1.800
Total followers (LinkedIn, X, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube)	667
Nº of promotional events organised by the project	6 (1 for citizens; 5 for engaged companies)

The progress and impact of the D&C actions will be evaluated in the upcoming D&C reports (M24 and M36) to provide a clearer understanding of the project's enhanced impact and visibility.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

This report summarises the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the first 12 months of the TWINNEDbySTARS project. The WP5 leader, in collaboration with all project partners, has been actively involved in the development and launch of materials and the implementation of associated activities in accordance with the strategy outlined in the TWINNEDbySTARS Dissemination and Communication Plan (D5.1).

Each communication and dissemination initiative has been designed to achieve specific objectives and address the project's key stakeholders, working in close cooperation with the WP1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan, and using various communication tools, including brochures, roll-ups and customised templates, to ensure a consistent message and a cohesive visual identity for the target audience.

Stakeholders have been regularly updated on the progress of TWINNEDbySTARS through the project website, events, social media channels, events, and newsletters.

Partners have been actively involved in project dissemination, with a special focus on the expansion of the TWINNEDbySTARS business network in the context of the product creation and capacity building activities foreseen in WP2 and WP3. The dissemination at local level has allowed TWINNEDbySTARS to contact specific stakeholders and to identify several companies interested and committed to participate in the different phases of the project.

It is relevant to underline that the project has achieved media coverage also thanks to the support of CINEA. The Agency has supported the dissemination of the project through the publication of several contents on its social networks and the inclusion of the first webinar, 'Stellar Tour', in the playlist of its YouTube channel, dedicated to the areas of Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture. It can be viewed at the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLrp3luGqStFAjpbU4i7Y5-vIIFLKGnoQV>

In addition, partnerships and contacts with related initiatives and projects have been established to further promote TWINNEDbySTARS (sister projects). The next step for WP5 will be to assess future joint collaborations in order to strengthen stakeholder involvement and maximise the exploitation of results with similar initiatives.

Finally, dissemination and communication activities are progressing according to plan. The next phase of WP5 will focus on optimising the results achieved so far, with emphasis on promoting more technical activities related to the next milestones of TWINNEDbySTARS. In particular, over the next year, special attention will be paid to the increase of social media followers, the promotion of additional dissemination events and synergies with relevant projects and initiatives at EU and OR levels.

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Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs

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Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101124900. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.